

NEW PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES AND THE PROFESSIONAL SKILLS OF TEACHERS

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Abstract. *The main goal of teaching forensic medicine at the bachelor's level is to acquire relevant knowledge and skills on issues directly or indirectly related to forensic medicine in future medical activities, in particular in the activities of general practitioners. The effectiveness of the educational process depends, on the one hand, on the professional training of teachers in the field, and on the other hand, on their pedagogical skills.*

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This aspect of educational activity is defined by the concept of the educational process. The educational process is understood as educational activity, in a narrow sense, as teaching aimed at a single goal. This is the main aspect of educational activity. However, it does not fully illuminate the content of learning activities. Educational activity, in a broad sense, includes, in addition to teaching, another important and responsible process - upbringing. Being an integral part of educational activity, it serves to form a number of necessary social qualities in students, and upbringing is considered two interconnected processes. They define two functions of educational activity - teaching and upbringing. Despite the fact that both processes, unlike each other, have their own specific goals and objectives, they serve, in essence, to ensure the perfection of members of one social profession - society. Thus, the future of each society is determined by the level of development of the education system, which is an integral part of it. In our country, which is steadily moving along the strategic path of strengthening independence and embarking on the path of economic liberalization, the reform of the education system, the introduction of advanced technologies from developed countries, the organization of education with the introduction of national values, and the thorough and effective implementation of this process have now been elevated to the level of state policy. In our country, the organizational, scientific, and methodological foundations for reforming the continuous education system have been created, and the main goal has been defined as the training of harmoniously developed individuals and highly qualified competitive specialists. The main components of the "National Program for Personnel Training" are the individual, the state and society, continuous education, science and production, which are interconnected. The implementation of the requirements of this document requires a radical restructuring of the education system, that is, a review of the conceptual provisions for the

development of public education and its positive solution in a short time. The solution of these tasks is directly related to the solution of the issues of what to extract from the vast information fund of the world scientific fund, how much and how to teach. In this context, modern problems related to the introduction of educational technologies become clear. Moreover, the times demand a broader continuation of work in this direction. The fact that some issues related to professional training are not well reflected in the practice of pedagogical education also makes the improvement of appropriate teaching methods an urgent issue. Currently, most methodologists and pedagogical scholars believe that pedagogical technologies fully guarantee the achievement of the intended goal in the education and upbringing of students. However, such statements cannot be accepted as objective truth, because the object is a person, whose consciousness cannot fully accept the proposed technology, and on the contrary, can even deny it. Therefore, when introducing modern pedagogical technologies into the educational process, only the teacher, who is its manager, becomes the main guarantor of achieving the intended goal. From this point of view, when introducing new pedagogical technologies and information and communication (ICT) technology, which is its main basis, into the education system, it is necessary to prioritize the level of training of the teacher as its manager. Therefore, the positive or expedient solution of most pressing problems on the agenda of pedagogical processes largely depends on the professional potential and pedagogical skills of the teacher. Such tasks as expanding the scale of introducing new pedagogical and information technologies into the educational process, introducing best practices in this area, drawing up and implementing specific plans in this area for each subject, transferring textbooks and teaching aids, as well as programs and lecture texts to electronic disks, ensuring their provision to every student, achieving the widespread introduction of modern pedagogical and information technologies in scientific and scientific-methodological work, as well as in the educational process, adequately providing the education system with the necessary information resources, and connecting educational institutions to communication networks are considered important. In short, pedagogical technology is the optimal organization of the educational process. The selection, processing, and modification of the form and volume of educational materials, adapted to the strength and learning characteristics of the student, are also related to educational technology. Pedagogical technology, in turn, is a system for developing and improving educational processes, the content, methods, and tools of education based on the objective laws and diagnostic goals of education, that is, it is an educational process that embodies the innovations of science and technology.

In recent years, much attention has been paid to the introduction of new advanced, innovative pedagogical technologies in the medical education system.

Consequently, it is undoubtedly necessary that the applied pedagogical technologies correspond to the content and essence of the training session, since the blind, random application of technological methods can not only be ineffective, and sometimes negatively affect the training session.

In the 2024-2025 academic year, the number of hours allocated for forensic medicine has been somewhat reduced, and 10 hours for lectures and 37 hours for practical classes have been allocated for the faculties of medical and medical pedagogy. Based on this, topics for lectures, practical classes, and independent work have been approved for the revised faculties. In particular, an 8-day schedule of training sessions has been created, and a new pedagogical complex suitable for use in these sessions has been determined at the department meeting. It should be noted that the selection and application of the appropriate type of pedagogical technology for a specific training session demonstrates a certain professional skill of the teacher.

The department teacher should be aware of the state and problems of medical practice in this area. Taking the above into account, blocks of new pedagogical technologies recommended by the department for each training session (4-5 methods in each block) have been compiled. The use of specific methods is decided by each teacher. As an example, in a practical training session on the topic "Mechanical Injuries," a block consisting of the technologies "Cluster," "Blitz-survey," "Assessment," "Step by step," and "Labyrinth" is recommended, and teachers can use several of them, depending on the level of student preparedness, the specifics of the training session, in particular, the objects of forensic medical examination.

In conclusion, the use of new innovative technologies corresponding to training sessions is an important factor in ensuring the assimilation of the topic by students.

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